

ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF A VIRTUAL REALITY TEACHER TRAINING APPLICATION: INSPIRED BY EDUCATORS, DESIGNED FOR EDUCATORS

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Abstract

The coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19) has created an educational crisis without precedent, posed new challenges to educational systems globally, and highlighted the need for teachers' upskilling along with the use of technology-based approaches to support the delivery of education and ensure the future of learning. In this context, the current paper aims to present the VRTEACHER project that proposes the use of digital technologies as part of teachers' training methodology. The vision of the project is to empower teachers' skills such as empathy, perspective-taking, self-efficacy, adaptability, etc. and readiness related to class management in crisis situations through Virtual Reality (VR) immersive and experiential training approaches that reflect real-life scenarios and situations. The aim and challenge of the project are not just to adapt the training provided to the digital era and connect it with new technologies but to build a holistic new approach to teacher training through the use of VR.

Keywords: Education, Teacher training, Virtual Reality, User involvement, Participatory design.

1 INTRODUCTION

The current paper aims to present the VRTEACHER project that proposes the use of digital technologies as part of teachers' training methodology. The idea behind the VRTEACHER project lies in previous work and research conducted in the past that investigated the potential of using VR in teacher training and education [1][2][3][4]. The main output of the project is a prototype VR training tool that has been designed 'from teachers for teachers'. The VRTEACHER project partners followed a three steps process to develop the project's competence framework and the training scenarios that were developed in the virtual environment (figure 1). Initially, an extensive review of existing competence frameworks for teachers was conducted (e.g., European Key Competencies Framework, DigCompEdu, ICT Competency Framework for Teachers New) to identify key skills and competences. Then a survey took place aiming to identify real teachers' needs and key skills in the post covid era. Based on the data gathered focus groups were conducted with expert educators, higher university students, and researchers to investigate in more depth teachers' needs, experiences during the pandemic and expectations of the VR training tool.

Figure 1. VRTEACHER project methodology.

For the establishment of the project's competence framework and the selection of the skills to be addressed through the VR-based training, the partnership took into consideration all the data gathered from the surveys

and focus groups but also the type of scenarios to be created and the limitation of the VR technology and equipment. After the identification of the scenarios to be created, the VR training tool was developed, and pilot tested with teachers in five different European countries (Cyprus, Greece, Spain, Malta and Ireland). As the analysis of the results is still in progress, no data will be presented in this paper. The results seem promising, and it is worth mentioning that teachers in all countries welcomed VR technology and supported this novel initiative that aims in the long term to be implemented as part of teacher training.

2 STATE OF THE ART: VIRTUAL REALITY IN EDUCATION

Immersive Virtual Reality (VR) systems generate a synthetic 3D environment in which the user interacts in real-time. Using head-mounted displays and pose tracking systems they deliver the illusion of an inclusive, extensive, surrounding, and vivid reality [5]. The user experiences the virtual environment as a place that he/she visits, rather than just images and animations displayed on a screen. In other words, the user experiences the sense of “being in the virtual reality”. This feeling is usually referred to as “presence”, as it is a unique property of immersive VR systems that can foster several educational opportunities.

Aviation companies and defense departments pioneered the use of VR in education. They exploited its possibilities to create realistic simulations for training pilots [6], and to develop decision-making skills to apply during military interventions [7]. The possibilities of VR technology to implement realistic simulations of high-risk situations in a safe environment have also been used for training surgical interventions [8], and emergency management [9]. VR can also be used to transport the learner to environments difficult or impossible to access and experience in real life, visualize different representations of educational material, and provide the educator with an environment that he/she can control, monitor and adapt in a way difficult to achieve in the real world [10]. These properties have been exploited by several VR educational applications for learning foreign languages [11], chemistry [12] or teaching training [13], for example.

In any case, the benefits that VR technology can report in education are not limited to the implementation of simulations. VR supports the design of educational activities following the principles of constructivist learning. According to this theory, knowledge is acquired through the interpretation of direct experience. VR supports well this notion, as the virtual environment can be explored and experienced in the first person, producing the illusion of a non-mediated interaction, similar to the real world, where learners conquer knowledge on their own [14]. In addition, VR technology can also report benefits in terms of the motivation of the learner [15]. More specifically, the intrinsic characteristics of the virtual 3D environment can stimulate motivational factors fundamentals for learning such as sensorial curiosity, fantasy and control [16]. Fostering motivation and cognitive engagement in the activity and the learning activity are fundamental factors in educational experiences as they increase attention and concentration in the activity, promoting the development of higher order thinking skills [17].

It is also necessary to highlight the opportunities that VR offers to support collaborative learning activities. Users who explore and interact with the same virtual environment experience the sense of “being there together”, even when located geographically dispersed. This feeling is also known as social presence [18], or co-presence. Users not only recognize the location in the environments of the other users, but also the actions they perform and can engage with them directly. In a collaborative VR learning environment, multiple learners interact simultaneously reinforcing their comprehension and understanding. The authors of [19] and [20] present two examples of systems that implement this educational approach for surgery training, and for helping to develop social communication amongst people with autism, respectively.

2.1 The VRTEACHER project

The VRTEACHER (Virtual Reality-based Training to improvE digitAl Competences of teachERs project is an ERASMUS+ project. The project aims to address the need for modernization and digital transformation of teacher education and training and reinforce educators’ digital skills and readiness through a Virtual Reality (VR) training method and tool. The project involves six partners, Cyprus University of Technology (Cyprus / Coordinator), University of the Aegean, University Carlos III of Madrid (Spain), Fundación Siglo22 (Spain), Future In Perspective Limited (Ireland), Commonwealth Centre for Connected Learning (Malta). More details about the project VRTEACHER project can be found on the official page of the project <https://www.vrteacher.eu/>.

The rationale behind the VRTEACHER project lies in the need for the transformation and modernization of education and the integration of technology-based approaches in teaching and learning. Additionally, in the last few years, teachers must teach in classrooms that have become more complex and multicultural than ever, while crisis situations like COVID-19 are adaptive and transformative challenges,

for which there are no guidelines to follow for appropriate responses [21]. The implementation of novel training approaches that will equip teachers with the life-long skills to manage classes in crisis situations is more imperative than ever. The teaching profession needs novel and ICT-based support tools that can empower teachers' skills and knowledge and promote the exchange of good practices ensuring the delivery of learning during crises, such as a pandemic.

In this context, the main objective of the VRTEACHER project is to promote the digitalization of teacher education by providing a novel VR-based approach. Using VR to train educators aims to promote their adaptability, readiness, and ability to respond and deal with crisis situations. By implementing VR-based approaches in teacher training the project aims to provide teachers with a safe and controllable space for experiential learning and practical training through immersive experiences that reflect real-life situations and challenges. Based on this approach, trainees experience certain problems faced by students, through the student's eyes, raising their awareness of in-class problematic situations. The main target groups of the project are in-service teachers/trainers/educators that need constant support and upskilling, and pre-service teachers/higher education students and future generations of teachers that need to acquire key competences including empathy, perspective-taking, self-efficacy, adaptability, etc. that will support their personal and professional development and the promotion of high-quality inclusive teaching practices enhanced with novel digital tools.

3 DESIGN PROCESS

It was essential for the VRTEACHER project to involve teachers during the project's activities as the main challenge was to design a VR training tool for teachers to teachers ensuring the added value and potential use of the VR tool. Teachers and other experts such as experts in ICT in education, experts in VR and researchers in the field of education and new technologies participated in the projects' activities, providing significant feedback to the partnership. Teachers were trained in the use of VR in education and pilot-tested the VR application to evaluate its effectiveness. The first step was to identify the real needs of teachers, particularly after the impact of the pandemic on teaching and learning. Then, the scenarios of the VR application were designed and developed in the VR world, that reflect real-life incidents and situations. The developed VR training tool was implemented in all five partner countries. The results are under analysis and therefore are not presented in the current paper.

3.1 Needs analysis and VRTEACHER competence framework

Under the VRTEACHER project, a questionnaire was designed to investigate the needs of teachers, particularly after the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The identification of teachers' real needs helped the consortium address those needs and provide a VR training tool of high quality and added value. The target group of the questionnaire was teachers and higher education students (potential teachers). The questionnaire had a total of 24 questions, divided into 4 different sections. The first section aimed to collect demographic data, such as the country of residence, gender, and the profile of participants. This second section collected information related to the challenges faced by both pre-service and in-service teachers during the pandemic and in virtual classrooms. The third and fourth sections gathered information related to key competences that were grouped into 3 general areas: Digital Competences, Personal Competences, and Civic Competences. Once the results were collected, a selection of key competences was made to work with the Virtual Reality tool developed under the project. The score obtained in each of the competences was considered; however, not all the highest-scoring competences were selected. To make this decision, the consortium had to take into consideration the strengths but also the limitation of VR technology and low-cost equipment that was decided to be used under this project during the preparation stage of the proposal to ensure that the VR application is accessible to the target audience. Those limitations led to the identification of the VRTEACHER competence framework and the development of suitable training scenarios that reflect reality and also address the real needs of teachers. The survey results revealed that the personal competences with the highest score by the participants (both teachers and students) were Stress resistance; Emotional control; and Self-control. The civic competences with the highest scores by the participants (both teachers and students) were Valuing diversity; "Trust" and "Cooperation"; "Social responsibility and engagement", "Sociability" and "Assertiveness". The digital competences with the highest scores from participants (both teachers and students) were: "Actively engaging learners"; "Problem-solving"; "Collaborative learning" and "understanding ICT in education".

After the end of the survey and the analysis of the results, the consortium conducted focus groups, to investigate in more depth, the needs of the target audience and their expectations of a VR training tool. Each partner country carried out a focus group with the target group consisting, in this case, of teachers

of any educational level, university students with an education degree, and ICT experts. The results revealed that COVID-19 affected teaching and learning by having to deliver the lessons online. Teachers identified disconnection from physical reality and the distance from students as major challenges. Regarding the video-call barriers, teachers mentioned the issue of activating the camera as a common problem. Having the cameras closed affected the lessons and teachers had no clue related to whether the students were listening during the lesson. As incidents, the participants reported that some of the students tried to interrupt the lessons by opening the microphone and playing music. Others pretended that the Internet connection had problems simulating noises to indicate that there were interruptions and some of them left the microphones open being the rest of the class able to hear what was happening in the home of the other. Moreover, there was very limited interaction with the participants, making it quite challenging to achieve motivation and engagement. Moreover, during the conversation, some of the participants mentioned that during face-to-face meetings they confronted cases of domestic violence.

Based on the survey and focus group results and having in mind the VR training tool that was going to be developed, the creation of the scenarios, possible limitations, and the possibility to assess the competences addressed in them, the competence framework of the project was identified. The final selection of the key competences to be addressed through the VRTEACHER training tool can be summarized in the following (figure 2):

Figure 2. Soft Skills of the VRTEACHER Framework.

3.2 Design of scenarios and app development.

The VRTEACHER application consists of 3 scenarios. Each scenario progresses and consists of three stages. Initially, the user is in the position of the teacher experiencing a crisis situation for a student during the lesson. After the end of the incident, the user changes virtual body and enters the virtual body of the student, experiencing once more the same crisis situation but through the eyes of the student this time. When this stage is over, the user enters again the virtual body of the teacher. The following diagram presents the way that each scenario progresses and what the user will have to deal with at each stage.

Figure 3. Scenario progression in the VR application.

Based on the scenarios the virtual environment was developed in the Unity game engine (figure 4).

Figure 4. VRTEACHER virtual environment.

3.3 Implementation activities.

The VRTEACHER application was implemented in five countries (Cyprus, Greece, Spain, Malta and Ireland). The training activities were conducted in three phases:

- One online/physical training workshop to familiarize teachers with VR technology, and its use in education and to present the VRTEACHER project.
- Face-to-face training sessions in groups, where teachers used the VRTEACHER application and were trained in the three developed scenarios.
- One final online/physical meeting to brainstorm on the VR-based training.

The impact of the VR application was evaluated through a questionnaire before the VR intervention, one after the training with the VR, and one follow-up questionnaire after 3 weeks of the training activities to assess the long-term impact of VR-based training. The results are under analysis and will be processed and presented as part of our future work.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The VRTEACHER project and deliverables were conceived based on the needs that arose due to the COVID-19 pandemic crisis but also having in mind that potential future crisis such as the war in Ukraine inevitably affects the delivery of education. The VR application was developed using a User-Centered Design (UCD), a process in which the partnership focused on the needs of teachers in the design process phase. The partnership identified real teachers' needs through literature review analysis, online surveys, and focus groups. Then the multidisciplinary team developed the three scenarios in a virtual reality environment to train teachers in a safe environment where wrong choices and reactions have no impact on real life and teachers can experiment repeatedly until they find the optimal solution from a pedagogical, psychological and legal point of view. The results that will identify the impact of the VR application on the personal and professional development of teachers are still under analysis. The first qualitative results based on the feedback of the teachers who participated in the pilot application show the need to develop more scenarios for dealing with crises that teachers face daily, such as "violent behaviour among students, from students and parents/guardians to teachers and vice versa"; "understanding the needs of students with special needs by experiencing in the virtual body how they perceive the world and how they perceive external stimuli"; and "rare cases that endanger the safety and life of school unit members such as natural disasters and extreme weather conditions". The project's research team is in the process of developing scenarios according to the needs expressed by teachers and has identified funding sources for the development of scenarios in a VR environment and further evaluation of the impact of the use of virtual reality for teacher training. The results of the analysis of the

questionnaires before and after the pilot application will reveal the impact and the added value of VR-based approaches in teacher training.

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